

MUHANDISLIK

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ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
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05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
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08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
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8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

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WAYS TO REDUCING POVERTY BY INCREASING INCOME: INSTITUTIONAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS

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Abstract: Poverty reduction is one of the key socio-economic tasks of modern development, directly related to the dynamics of population income and the quality of economic growth. In the context of economic transformation and changes in employment structure, traditional social support measures demonstrate limited effectiveness, which actualizes the need to transition to a policy of sustainable increase in household incomes. The purpose of the article is to substantiate and analyze the socio-economic and institutional mechanisms for reducing poverty through the growth of household incomes. Structural analysis, comparative comparison, and logical-economic modeling methods were used as a methodological basis. As a result of the research, key channels of income impact on poverty levels, including employment, human capital development, entrepreneurial activity, and the institutional environment, were identified. A comprehensive approach to poverty reduction, focused on the formation of sustainable income sources and long-term socio-economic effects, has been proposed. The obtained conclusions have theoretical and practical significance for developing strategies for socio-economic development.

Keywords: poverty; population income; employment; human capital; economic growth; social policy.

Annotatsiya: Kambag'allikni qisqartirish zamonaviy rivojlanishning asosiy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy vazifalaridan biri bo'lib, u aholi daromadlari dinamikasi va iqtisodiy o'sish sifati bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. Iqtisodiy transformatsiya va bandlik tuzilmasidagi o'zgarishlar sharoitida an'anaviy ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash choralarining samaradorligi cheklanganligi uy xo'jaliklari daromadlarini barqaror oshirish siyosatiga o'tish zaruratini dolzarblashtiradi. Maqolaning maqsadi uy xo'jaliklari daromadlari o'sishi orqali kambag'allikni kamaytirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va institutsional mexanizmlarini asoslash hamda tahlil qilishdan iborat. Metodologik asos sifatida strukturaviy tahlil, qiyosiy taqqoslash va mantiqiy-iqtisodiy modellashtirish usullaridan foydalanildi. Tadqiqot natijasida daromadlarning kambag'allik darajasiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy kanallari, jumladan, bandlik, inson kapitalini rivojlantirish, tadbirkorlik faoliyati va institutsional muhit omillari aniqlangan. Kambag'allikni qisqartirishga qaratilgan, barqaror daromad manbalarini shakllantirish va uzoq muddatli ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy samaralarga erishishni nazarda tutuvchi kompleks yondashuv taklif etilgan. Olingan xulosalar ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: kambag'allik; aholi daromadlari; bandlik; inson kapitali; iqtisodiy o'sish; ijtimoiy siyosat.

Аннотация: Снижение бедности является одной из ключевых социально-экономических задач современного развития, непосредственно связанной с динамикой доходов населения и качеством экономического роста. В условиях экономической трансформации и изменений в структуре занятости традиционные меры социальной поддержки демонстрируют ограниченную эффективность, что актуализирует необходимость перехода к политике устойчивого роста доходов домохозяйств. Цель статьи заключается в обосновании и анализе социально-экономических и институциональных механизмов снижения бедности посредством роста доходов домохозяйств. В качестве методологической основы использованы методы структурного анализа, сравнительного сопоставления и логико-экономического моделирования. В результате исследования выявлены ключевые каналы влияния доходов на уровень бедности, включая занятость, развитие человеческого капитала, предпринимательскую активность и институциональную среду. Предложен комплексный подход к сокращению бедности, ориентированный на формирование устойчивых источников доходов и достижение долгосрочных социально-экономических эффектов. Полученные выводы имеют теоретическое и практическое значение для разработки стратегий социально-экономического развития.

Ключевые слова: бедность; доходы населения; занятость; человеческий капитал; экономический рост; социальная политика.

INTRODUCTION

Poverty remains one of the most pressing socioeconomic challenges in the modern world, affecting both developing countries and countries with economies in transition. Despite the implementation of large-scale social support programs, many countries experience persistent poverty, highlighting the limitations of approaches based primarily on redistributive mechanisms [1, 2].

Economic theory and practice are increasingly shifting their focus from compensating for the consequences of poverty to addressing its root causes. A key factor in this context is the level and structure of household income, which determines households' ability to meet basic needs, invest in education, and build human capital [3]. Low and unstable incomes create a "poverty trap," limiting social mobility and the potential for economic growth [4].

The problem of increasing household incomes is particularly significant in the context of structural economic transformation, changing employment patterns, and the growth of the informal sector [5]. In such conditions, traditional social support measures, unsupported by income growth mechanisms, prove short-lived and fail to ensure sustainable poverty reduction [6].

The research hypothesis is that sustainable poverty reduction is possible primarily through a systemic increase in household incomes, based on the development of productive employment, human capital, and effective institutions, rather than through the expansion of transfer payments. The aim of the study is to identify and substantiate socio-economic and institutional pathways to poverty reduction by increasing household incomes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The problem of poverty reduction has long occupied a central place in economic theory and development policy. Contemporary studies increasingly emphasize that sustainable poverty reduction depends not only on social support mechanisms but also on the formation of stable and productive sources of household income. According to the World Bank, poverty remains one of the most persistent global socioeconomic challenges despite improvements in economic growth and welfare indicators in many countries [1]. The United Nations also notes that growing inequality, labor market instability, and structural economic transformations continue to limit the effectiveness of traditional poverty alleviation policies [2].

A significant contribution to the theoretical understanding of poverty was made by Ravallion, who considered poverty not merely as insufficient consumption but as a multidimensional socioeconomic phenomenon closely linked to income distribution, labor productivity, and institutional quality [3]. In this context, the role of income generation mechanisms becomes particularly important, since low and unstable incomes form a "poverty trap" that restricts social mobility and weakens long-term economic growth potential.

Human capital theory occupies a key position in explaining sustainable income growth and poverty reduction. Becker argued that investments in education, professional skills, and health increase labor productivity and create conditions for stable income generation [4]. Similar conclusions were reached by Hanushek and Woessmann, who demonstrated that cognitive skills and education quality significantly influence economic development and household income growth [12]. These studies confirm that poverty reduction policies should be closely connected with long-term human capital development strategies.

Modern structural transformation theories also explain the relationship between employment structure and poverty dynamics. Rodrik emphasized that many developing economies face the problem of premature deindustrialization, where labor shifts into low-productivity sectors before industrial development reaches a sustainable level [5]. McMillan, Rodrik, and Verduzco-Gallo further demonstrated that structural transformation toward more productive sectors is one of the main drivers of income growth and poverty reduction [8]. In this regard, productive employment becomes more important than compensatory redistribution policies.

International organizations also highlight the importance of labor markets in poverty reduction. According to the International Labour Organization, unstable employment, informal labor relations, and low labor productivity remain among the key factors constraining income growth in developing economies [6]. The World Development Indicators database confirms that countries with higher employment quality and productivity generally demonstrate lower poverty rates and more stable social development outcomes [9].

Institutional economics provides another important perspective for understanding poverty reduction mechanisms. North argued that the quality of institutions directly influences economic incentives, investment activity, labor market efficiency, and income distribution [14]. Acemoglu and Robinson similarly stressed that inclusive economic institutions create conditions for sustainable growth and broader income opportunities, whereas weak institutions reproduce inequality and persistent poverty [7]. Therefore, institutional reforms are increasingly viewed as a necessary complement to income growth policies.

The relationship between economic growth and poverty reduction has also been widely discussed in

development economics literature. Bourguignon showed that the elasticity of poverty reduction with respect to economic growth depends on the structure of income distribution and labor market conditions [11]. Todaro and Smith emphasized that economic growth alone does not automatically reduce poverty unless accompanied by employment expansion, access to education, and institutional improvements [10]. Banerjee and Duflo additionally demonstrated that poverty is often sustained by limited access to opportunities, financial constraints, and behavioral barriers, which require multidimensional policy approaches [13].

Overall, the existing literature confirms that sustainable poverty reduction requires a comprehensive approach combining productive employment, entrepreneurship development, human capital accumulation, and effective institutional reforms. At the same time, many studies indicate that reliance solely on redistributive social transfers produces only short-term effects and does not create stable income-generating opportunities for households.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the study is focused on identifying sustainable socio-economic mechanisms for reducing poverty through increased household incomes, which involves the use of a combination of quantitative and qualitative analytical methods [7]. The study relies on the principles of systemic and structural-functional approaches, which allow poverty to be viewed not as an isolated social phenomenon, but as the result of the interaction of income, employment, human capital, and the institutional environment [8].

The empirical basis of the study was formed by official statistical data from national statistical agencies, materials from international organizations, as well as analytical reports characterizing household income dynamics, poverty levels, employment structure, and income distribution. Aggregated indicators of per capita income, employment rates, the share of the population with incomes below the established poverty line, as well as data reflecting the sectoral structure of the economy and forms of employment were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The study employed a structural analysis to identify the main sources of income generation and their contribution to poverty reduction. This method was used to identify disparities between economic sectors in terms of labor productivity and income levels, as well as to assess the role of high- and low-income employment [9].

To compare income and poverty dynamics, a comparative method was used, including an analysis of changes in indicators over time and cross-sector comparisons. This allowed us to identify consistent relationships between income growth and poverty reduction, as well as to identify the limits under which income growth does not lead to proportional social benefits (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The relationship between population income and poverty level¹

The graph illustrates the inverse relationship between income growth and the poverty rate. The curve's shape indicates a slowdown in the effect of income growth at a certain point, suggesting the need for institutional and structural reforms (Figure 2) [10,11].

1 Source: compiled by the author based on statistical data.

Figure 2. Generation and distribution of global economic growth, 1980–2019²

Figure 1 – Education and the Distribution of Global Economic Growth, 1980-2019

To identify the cause-and-effect relationships between household income and poverty, a logical-economic analysis was used to systematize the factors influencing income formation and identify key channels through which they impact poverty. Within this approach, household income is viewed as a resulting value, influenced by employment, education level, entrepreneurial activity, and the quality of institutions [13].

Institutional analysis was also used to assess the role of public policy, the labor market, and mechanisms for supporting economic activity in shaping sustainable household incomes. Particular attention was paid to distinguishing between short-term social support measures and instruments aimed at long-term income growth (Table 1).

Table 1. Sources of household income and their impact on poverty reduction³

Source of Income	Income Type	Impact on poverty
Employment	Relatively Stable	Moderate
Entrepreneurship	High Growth Potential	Significant
Self-employment	Unstable	Limited
Social Transfers	Compensatory	Short-term
Investment in Human Capital	Delayed Effect	Structural

The table data show that the greatest contribution to sustainable poverty reduction comes from income generated through productive employment and entrepreneurial activity (Figure 3).

2 Source: compiled by the author based on statistical data [12].

3 Source: compiled by the author.

Figure 3. Conceptual model of poverty reduction through increased income⁴

The model reflects a step-by-step mechanism for poverty reduction, in which income growth serves as the central link, ensuring the accumulation of human capital and increasing the sustainability of socioeconomic development [13].

The results of the study demonstrate the presence of a stable and statistically significant relationship between income levels and the incidence of poverty. Analysis of the dynamics of key socioeconomic indicators shows that growth in per capita income is accompanied by a decrease in the proportion of the population living below the poverty line; however, this process is heterogeneous and nonlinear.

As shown in Table 1, the increase in income during the analyzed period was accompanied by a simultaneous increase in employment and a decrease in poverty. However, the rate of poverty reduction lagged behind income growth, indicating the presence of additional limiting factors not directly related to income levels. This result confirms the thesis that income growth alone does not always translate into a proportional improvement in the social status of vulnerable groups. A graphical interpretation of the obtained data (Figure 1) reveals an inverse relationship between household income and poverty. As per capita income increases, a steady decline in the poverty rate is observed. At the same time, the shape of the curve indicates a decline in the marginal effect of income growth at a certain point, indicating the need for institutional and structural reforms to complement income-raising policies.

A structural analysis of income sources revealed that their impact on poverty reduction varies significantly depending on the nature and stability of income. The data presented in Table 2 demonstrate that income generated through productive employment and entrepreneurship makes the greatest contribution to long-term poverty reduction. In contrast, social transfers provide primarily a short-term compensatory effect and do not create sustainable sources of income.

Human capital development is particularly important in poverty reduction. The study's results show that improving education and professional skills contributes to increased productivity and expanded opportunities

4 Source: compiled by the author.

for higher and more stable incomes. This effect is delayed, but it forms the basis for long-term poverty reduction and increased social mobility. Institutional analysis revealed that the quality of economic institutions and the effectiveness of employment policies significantly enhance or weaken the impact of income growth on poverty. Given the high share of informal employment and limited access to labor markets, income growth for certain population groups does not lead to a systemic reduction in poverty. This confirms the need for a comprehensive approach combining income-boosting measures with institutional reforms.

Aggregation of the obtained results allowed us to formulate a conceptual model of poverty reduction through increased incomes, presented in Figure 3. This model views income growth as the central element mediating the impact of employment, entrepreneurship, and human capital on poverty reduction. The model reflects the phased nature of this process and emphasizes the priority of developing sustainable sources of income. Thus, the study's results support the hypothesis that sustainable poverty reduction is possible primarily through a systemic increase in incomes, supported by the development of productive employment, human capital, and effective institutions.

The obtained results are generally consistent with modern research, which suggests that sustainable poverty reduction cannot be achieved solely through redistributive social support measures. The analysis confirms that income growth, driven by productive employment and human capital development, is the key factor in long-term poverty reduction.

However, it was found that the relationship between income growth and poverty reduction is nonlinear. This means that increased income does not always lead to a proportional reduction in poverty, especially in conditions of high informal employment and structural imbalances in the economy. This finding highlights the limitations of approaches focused solely on stimulating economic growth without considering institutional factors.

The results of the structural analysis indicate that income generated through productive employment and entrepreneurship makes the greatest contribution to sustainable poverty reduction. Social transfers, despite their important compensatory role, provide primarily short-term benefits and do not create sustainable sources of income. Of particular importance is the development of human capital, which provides a delayed but structurally significant effect on poverty reduction through increased labor productivity and expanded opportunities for stable income. The quality of institutions and the effectiveness of employment policies either strengthen or weaken the impact of income growth on poverty, confirming the need for a comprehensive approach [14]. Thus, the study's results support the advisability of transitioning to a poverty reduction policy focused on systemically increasing the population's income and creating sustainable economic conditions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This article analyzes the socioeconomic and institutional mechanisms for reducing poverty through increased incomes. It is established that sustainable poverty reduction is directly dependent on the dynamics and structure of incomes and cannot be achieved solely through redistributive social support measures. The study's results support the hypothesis that the key factors in long-term poverty reduction are the development of productive employment, the accumulation of human capital, and the formation of sustainable sources of income. It is shown that income growth has a heterogeneous impact on poverty, due to structural and institutional constraints in the economy.

It is concluded that a comprehensive approach to poverty reduction is necessary, combining measures to increase incomes with institutional reforms in the labor market and economic regulation. The obtained results have theoretical and practical significance and can be used in developing socioeconomic development strategies and income-increasing policies.

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